

The Impact of Perceived Value and Attitude towards Purchase Intention at Sambel Branding Restaurant

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ABSTRACT: Sambal is a traditional Indonesian spice that has been an essential component of Indonesian cuisine for centuries. Today, it is considered a staple spice in all Indonesian dishes. The popularity of sambal has attracted many new restaurants of varying scales to enter the spicy food market and utilize the "Sambel" brand as their restaurant attraction. Jakarta, which is one of the eight primary cities in Indonesia, ranks fourth with the most restaurant dine-in visits in 2022. As per the data provided by the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), there are 6,780 restaurant units in Indonesia of medium to large scale. Jakarta secures the top spot as the province with the most medium-scale restaurants in Indonesia, with 3,062 units in 2021. Sambel Korek DNO is one of the dining places in Jakarta with the Sambel, the central outlet is located in Sumur Batu Kemayoran. This establishment is the highest contributor to the sales of Sambel Korek DNO as compared to other establishments. The significant consumption levels of Jakartans and their fondness for spicy cuisine drive new entries to launch their street food stalls, small establishments, and restaurants under the Sambel brand, causing an increase in competition. However, the sales of DNO Korek Sambal did not meet the target this year due to a decline in the number of customers dining at this outlet. This could be attributed to low brand awareness, as many other eateries also use the "Sambel" branding. Additionally, customers' perception of quality may be influenced by the similarity in offerings with other major players in the "Sambel" market, such as Waroeng SS and Sambal Bakar Indonesia. This research wants to analyze whether perceived value and attitude could mediate brand awareness and perceived quality toward purchase intention for potential customers and existing customers. This research is conducted using SPSS and PLS-SEM. Resulting that Attitude has no mediating effects on brand awareness and perceived quality towards purchase intention. However, perceived quality has mediating effects on brand awareness and perceived quality towards attitude, which has a significant influence on purchase intention.

KEYWORDS: Attitude, Brand Awareness, Perceived Quality, Perceived Value, Purchase Intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

Jakarta, Indonesia's capital city, is the most populous city in the country and the second-largest urban area in the world. Jakarta's population was over 10.6 million in 2020 and a annual growth rate of 0.66%. In 2022, Jakarta had a population density of over 16,000 people per square kilometer (JakartaProv-CSIRT, 2022). Out of Indonesia's eight major cities, Jakarta has the fourth-highest number of restaurant visits for dine-in in 2022 (Pusparisa, 2020). According to data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), there were 6,780 medium to large-scale restaurant units in Indonesia; Jakarta holds the first position for the province with the most medium-scale restaurants in Indonesia, with 3,062 units in 2021 [3] Jakarta also has the highest average food expenditure among urban residents, with 953.32 thousand rupiah/per capita/per month (Viva, 2022)

A survey by Populix revealed that most Gen Z and millennials prefer dining out or buying takeaway instead of preparing meals at home. They typically dine in or order takeout. About 63% of respondents purchase food offline 1-3 times a month, while 21% order food online 2-3 times a month [5]. Jakarta's large population, high spending on food, and the preference of Gen Z and millennials to buy food rather than cook it themselves are driving growth in the food and beverage service sector, including food outlets that sell spicy foods such as sambal as the condiment

In Indonesian food culture, "Sambel" or "Sambal" has been an essential part of it for hundreds of years. Sambal is a condiment that is considered an essential accompaniment to every meal in Indonesia. There are different regions of Indonesia with their own version of Sambel. Java Island has the highest number of Sambal variants. About 64.5% of Sambal are found in Indonesia[6]. This has caused many new restaurants, from small scale to medium to large scale, to enter the spicy dining market and use the branding

"Sambel"/"Sambal" as the attraction of their restaurants, big competitors such as Waroeng SS and Sambal Bakar Indonesia also continue to improve their restaurants.

A. *Company Profile*

Sambel Korek DNO is one of the spicy eating places with "Sambel" branding established in 2016 in Kemayoran, Central Jakarta, by Dwi Laksono, a native of Bojonegoro. Initially, the concept was a street food. Over time Sambel Korek DNO continued to grow rapidly and established outlets in several areas in Jakarta. Sambel Korek DNO is an Indonesian restaurant that serves various types of Sambel Korek and their derivatives alongside a wide array of typical Indonesian side dishes. Sambel Korek, which originated from Bojonegoro, Indonesia, is a type of chili sauce that is part of the many variations of chili sauce found in Indonesia. Its distinctiveness lies in its textured consistency and the addition of hot oil.

B. *Business Issue*

Sambel Korek DNO has six branches spread across the DKI Jakarta area and its surroundings. The Sambel Korek DNO central outlet is on Jl. Sumur Batu Raya no 415 in the Kemayoran area, Central Jakarta City. According to the Vice President of Business, Vice President of Human Resources, and Supervisor of Business Development Sambel Korek DNO, sales during this year, except during Ramadhan, did not reach the target. In previous years, Sambel Korek DNO sales could get around 10-12 million rupiah per day. Based on the interview results, the sales target for 2023 is to reach an average of 12 million rupiah per day, but sales this year are in the average range of 7-8 million rupiah per day.

The high consumption level of Jakarta residents and the public's preference for spicy food encourage newcomers to establish street foods, small outlets, and restaurants with Sambel branding, thus increasing competition. In the Kemayoran sub-district, more than 15 dine-in places have "Sambal" or "Sambel" branding. In addition to competing with big player brands in the spicy food segment, such as Waroeng SS and Sambal Bakar Indonesia, Sambel Korek DNO must continue to intensify its innovation and marketing efforts.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *Brand Awareness*

Brand Awareness, the foundation of Brand Equity, is the ability of the consumer to identify, recognize, or recall the brand within the category at a level of detail sufficient to make a purchase. Brand awareness is an outcome of the marketing stimuli such as brand exposure. Anything that brings the brand to the consumer's attention and focus can enhance brand awareness [7]. Research has consistently shown a direct relationship between brand awareness and a consumer purchase intention [8][9]. Elevated brand awareness leads to informed purchase decisions and increased likelihood of purchase. While research on the relationship between brand awareness and perceived value has yielded mixed results, with some studies indicating no significant association and others suggesting a weak positive correlation, brand awareness remains an invaluable marketing asset due to its established impact on purchase intention [10]. Additionally, brand awareness has influenced consumer attitudes [11] [12]. When a brand has a high level of awareness, strong associations, and customer loyalty, it has an impact on customer behaviour [13].

B. *Perceived Quality*

The evaluation of a customer's overall value of a product, based on their personal perception, is referred to as perceived quality. It's important to note that this definition differs from objective or actual quality. When referring to perceived quality, it's a global assessment that's often comparable to an attitude. Essentially, it's a judgment that consumers typically evoke when considering a product. In other words, quality is defined in the model as the consumer's assessment regarding the superiority or excellence of a product. [14]. When consumers perceive the high quality of the offered product/service, it tends to have a high perceived value [15]. According to [16] (JEON & YOO, 2021), perceived quality significantly impacts perceived value. Previous studies in the restaurant industry have found that customers' perceptions of the quality of the restaurant's atmosphere can influence consumers' emotions and impact consumers' satisfaction and other attitudes and behavioral intentions [18] (Khan et al., 2019) In addition, a summary of previous research indicates that several factors, such as service quality, food quality, restaurant atmosphere, infrastructure, and customer orientation can influence perceived quality [18].

C. Perceived Value

Consumers tend to evaluate the perceived value of a product in relation to the price incurred by customers [20]. Perceived value is essentially the consumer's perception of whether the product can satisfy their needs and meet their expectations. A product's value can be measured in four dimensions. The first dimension is price value, which is the benefit of a product due to its perceived cost reduction in both the short and long term. The second dimension is functional value, which is the benefit of a product due to its perceived quality and expected performance. The third dimension is emotional value, which is the benefit of a product due to the feelings or affective states that purchasing it generates. The fourth dimension is social value, which is the benefit of a product due to its ability to enhance one's social self-concept. These dimensions provide a comprehensive understanding of the benefits a product can offer [21] [22] [23]. Based on previous researches, perceived value could influence consumers' purchase intention and customer attitude [22] [23][24][25]. In this research, the author is focusing on price value and emotional value.

D. Attitude

An individual's attitude is comprised of their lasting assessment, emotional response, and behavioral tendencies towards an idea or object. It can lead to either a positive or negative disposition towards the subject and prompt one to either move closer or further away from it. Attitude influences a person's consistent behavior towards similar objects, but it can be difficult to alter since it requires both energy and thought. It is generally recommended that a company aligns its products with existing attitudes rather than attempting to change them.[7]. Attitudes were evaluated as either positive or negative towards food products, which directly impacted the purchase intention of the consumer. The more favorable the attitude, the stronger the consumer's intent to purchase. It is also reported that attitude has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention [25] [26] [27] [28].

E. Purchase Intention

According to previous studies purchase intention is a consumer behavior that involves selecting or buying products based on their experience, usage, and desire [7]. The intention behind the purchase indicator can be categorized into four types. Firstly, transactional interest pertains to consumers who intend to purchase a product. Secondly, referential interest is observed when consumers tend to provide references or recommendations for a product to others. Thirdly, preferential interest pertains to the consumers who aim to choose a particular product as their first choice during shopping activities. Finally, exploratory interest is observed when consumers aim to gather more information about a product before making the purchase [29].

F. Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework refers to a set of interlinked assumptions, beliefs, and expectations that guide research. It is a tentative theory that determines what will be measured and what statistical relationships to look forward in a theoretical framework. Conceptual frameworks are critical in inductive theory-building exploratory studies, while theoretical frameworks are crucial in deductive, theory-testing studies[30]. Figure.1 shows a conceptual framework designed on the basis of the previous theoretical foundation and literature review to address the marketing issue at Sambel Korek DNO. The conceptual framework is used to interlink the hypothesis that the author wants to analyze.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

The author has developed several hypotheses based on the literature review and the conceptual framework.

H1: Brand Awareness has positive and significant effect towards Perceived Value

H2: Brand Awareness has positive and significant effect towards Attitude

H3: Perceived Quality has a positive and significant relationship towards perceived value

H4: Perceived Quality has a positive and significant relationship towards attitude

H5: Perceived Value has a positive and significant effects towards attitude.

H6: Attitude has a positive and significant effects towards purchase intention

H7a: Attitude has a mediating effects on Brand Awareness towards Purchase Intention

H7b: Attitude has a mediating effects on Perceived Quality towards Purchase Intention

H8a: Perceived Value has mediating effects on brand awareness and attitude

H8b: Perceived Value has mediating effects on perceived quality and attitude

III. METHODOLOGY

This research is carried out using the survey with questionnaires. A questionnaire is a structured approach to the collection of data that consists of written or verbal questions to be answered by the respondents. To measure consumer attitudes, the research used a widely used five-point Likert scale. Respondents were asked to indicate how much they agreed or disagreed on a continuum from 1 (strongly disagree) until 5 (strongly agree) [31]. In this research, the population consists of Jabodetabek area residents who have a preference for spicy food, the majority of whom are between the ages of 17 and 74. The first stage consists of creating a quota of population elements, which in this study uses a minimum limit of 200 people. In the second stage, the sample elements were determined based on convenience or judgement, which in this study used a 50:50 composition between existing consumers and potential consumers of Sambel Korek DNO to gain better insights from both groups.

The author conducted statistical analysis using SPSS and PLS-SEM. The data encompassed 207 respondents who were divided into two distinct categories: existing customers and potential customers. Of the total respondents, 111 were existing customers, which are those who had purchased from Sambel Korek DNO, while the remaining 96 were potential customers, which are those who had not yet purchased from Sambel Korek DNO. In a previous study, a pre-test was conducted using partial least square structural equation modelling with 30 participants, and a small survey was selected as a pilot study to test the methodology before conducting the full study. The data collected was then utilized for measurement purposes [32]. The author carried out the pilot testing of 34 respondents consists of 17 existing customers and 17 potential customers. SPSS is used to analyze variable descriptive Statistics and variable Inferential Statistics. A variable plays a critical role in analysing statistical data. Descriptive statistics serves as a tool to present a succinct summary of the sample being studied, without drawing any inferences based on probability theory [33]. It pertains to a particular attribute or characteristic of a sample or population member, which may differ in quality or quantity from that of another. Inferential statistics are used for drawing inferences and making generalisations about a larger population of subjects, based on measurements obtained from a sample of subjects in the experiment. The suitability of different types of inferential statistics depends on the study design and sample characteristics. Hence, it is essential to consider these factors when selecting an appropriate statistical method for a given research study [34]. After those analysis, the author used PLS-SEM to analyze hypothesis testing. [35][36].

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. *Variability and Reability Testing of Pilot Testing*

The sample size for pilot testing, it is generally considered appropriate to have a sample size of 30 to 100 respondents [31]. In a previous study, a small-scale survey was conducted as a pilot testing using PLS-SEM with 30 respondents. This was done as a trial study before conducting a full-fledged study. The responses collected from the survey were used to measure the effectiveness of the study [32] In this analysis, the author uses PLS-SEM for the quantitative analysis of customer data. The pilot study included a total sample of 34 respondents, with an equal proportion of 17 potential customers and 17 existing customers. The acceptance criteria used are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Acceptance Criteria of Variability and Reliability Testing

Categories.	Indexes	Asumptions	References
Internal Reliability	Outer loadings	Outer Loading > 0.7	[36]
Internal Consistency Reliability	Cronbach's alpha and Composite Reliability	Cronbach's alpha > 0.7 Composite Reliability > 0.7	[35] [37]
Convergent Validity	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	AVE > 0.5	[38]
Discriminant Validity	Cross Loading Larcker's Fornel	Cross loading: the construct have to be the highest among all other items in the scale Fornell Larcker: The square root of the AVE of each construct must be greater than its highest correlation with any of the other constructs.	(Hair et al., 2017) (Fornell & Larcker, 1981)

Outer loading values reflect reliability in construction, which should be greater than 0.7. In addition, the squared value of the standard coefficient of loadings may be used to calculate the degree to which the measure is described by endogenous items in the model. The value of the loadings, in conjunction with the AVE value, is used to obtain convergent validity for the scale. Acceptable AVEs are .50 and above, indicating that the construct can explain at least 50% of the variance in its items [39]. The analysis shows that the Cronbach's alpha requirements are >0.7 and the composite reliability (rho_c) is greater than 0.7. In terms of AVE, the value is greater than 0.5. After following the acceptance criteria, the final results of the validity and reliability of Pilot Testing are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Graphical output of Validation and Reliability test in Pilot Testing

B. Descriptive Analysis

In this section, we will perform a descriptive analysis of the results obtained from the questionnaire to gain insights into consumer behavior, including their geographic and demographic profiles, as well as their dine-in behavior. The data collected will help align the marketing strategies with the needs and preferences of our current and potential customers. Additionally, descriptive statistics on each research variable is used to determine if the PLS-SEM analysis will be conducted by combining existing and potential customers or separately.

B.1. Demographic Profile

According to the obtained data, 93.2% of the 207 participants have dined at "Sambel"/"Sambal" branded restaurants, and of all participants, 53.6% have tried the DNO Korek Sambel product. The majority of the customers, at 52.2%, belonged to the age group of 18-24, followed by the 25-34 age group at 34.3%. Additionally, 60.9% of respondents from Jakarta, whereas 23.5% of respondents from the Jabodetabek area. The study's results show that the largest percentage of participants, accounting for 41.5%, are employed. Students make up 32.4% and are the second most represented group. Respondents generally come from low-middle socioeconomic backgrounds. Monthly expenses range between IDR 2,000,000 and IDR 5,000,000, and 28.5% of respondents are in this category.

B.2. Consumer Behaviour of Sambal Restaurant

From the survey, 53.6% of respondents reported eating out 1-3 times a week. The majority spend between Rp. 25,000 to Rp. 40,000 when dining out. In terms of dine in frequency with the "Sambal" branding, respondents reported eating there 1-3 times per month. Instagram is the top platform for brand awareness. A survey found that 36% of existing customers and 24% of potential customers learned about the brand through Instagram. Word of mouth from friends contributed to 27.9% of existing customers and 12.5% of potential customers. The survey also showed that 28.1% of potential customers are not yet aware of the brand.

B.3. Variable Descriptive Analysis

A characteristic of a sample or population that can vary in quantity or quality is known as a variable. Descriptive statistics summarise the analysed sample without making inferences based on probability theory. [40]. Compare Means is used to compare multiple numeric variables using one or more categorical variables. It is particularly useful for the simultaneous summary of numeric variables across categories. The result of means comparative could be seen at Table 2.

Table 2. Results of Variable Means Comparative

<i>Variables.</i>	<i>Potential Customers</i>	<i>Existing Customers</i>	<i>Score Gap</i>
Brand Awareness	2.42	4.29	1.87
Perceived Quality	4	4.56	0.56
Perceived Value	3.87	4.56	0.69
Attitude	3.65	4.48	0.83
Purchase Intention	3.58	4.46	0.88

The normality test in SPSS 27 software determines if a dataset is normally distributed. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests were utilized for this purpose. For sample sizes greater than or equal to 50, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is recommended, whereas the Shapiro-Wilk test is more suitable for small sample sizes. A P-value (labeled as "Sig." in the SPSS output) greater than 0.05 indicates normal distribution [41], [42]. Table 3 below shows that all variables are not normally distributed. Therefore, a Mann-Whitney Test was the suitable test to determine any differences between both groups.

Table 3. Normality Test Results

<i>Customers</i>	<i>p-value (Kolmogorov-Smirnov)^a</i>	<i>p-value (Shapiro-Wilk)</i>
BA- Potential Customers	0.142	0.003
BA- Existing Customers	0.000	0.000
PQ- Potential Customers	0.000	0.000
PQ- Existing Customers	0.000	0.000
PV- Potential Customers	0.000	0.000
PV- Existing Customers	0.000	0.000
AT-Potential Customers	0.001	0.000
AT- Existing Customers	0.000	0.000
PI- Potential Customers	0.001	0.001
PI- Existing Customers	0.000	0.000

^a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

The Mann-Whitney test is a statistical method that compares the distributions of two groups. It does not require a large normal sample. SPSS calculates the Mann-Whitney value and converts it to the Z-value. Differences between the two groups are calculated by Asymp. Sig (two-tailed). The table 4 shows significant differences between the existing customers and potential customers, as indicated with Asymp. Sig value <0.05 [43]. Therefore, PLS-SEM analysis will be conducted separately for both groups.

Table 4. Test Statistics Mann-Whitney U Test

	<i>BA</i>	<i>PQ</i>	<i>PV</i>	<i>AT</i>	<i>PI</i>
Mann-Whitney U	779.500	3104.000	2381.500	2308.000	2340.000
Wilcoxon W	5435.500	7760.000	7037.500	6964.000	6996.000
Z	-10.616	-5.257	-7.025	-7.124	-7.106
Asymp. Sig (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

C. Hypothesis Testing

Before conducting hypothesis testing with PLS-SEM, it is essential to evaluate the validity and reliability of all data as per the results obtained from the pilot testing. The model structure, also referred to as the inner model within the PLS-SEM context, connects the constructs (circles or ovals) and displays the relationships (paths) among them. The measurement model of a construct, also named the outer model in PLS-SEM, exhibits the correlation between the construct and its indicator variables (rectangles). There are two types of measurement models: one for the exogenous latent variables (i.e., the constructs that elucidate other constructs in the model) and one for the endogenous latent variables (i.e., the constructs being explained in the model).[38].

In this study, the author analyze both group separately. The first group consists of 96 potential customers. Potential customers are target segments that have the potential to become customers of Sambel Korek DNO but have never bought at Sambel Korek DNO. While the second groups consists of 111 existing customers. Existing customers are people that have experienced dine in at Sambel Korek DNO. The result of Hypothesis testing could be seen in Table 5 and Table 6.

Table 5. Path Coefficient Comparison of Direct Effects

	<i>Potential Customers</i>		<i>Existing Customers</i>		<i>Conclusion</i>
	<i>T statistics</i>	<i>P values</i>	<i>T statistics</i>	<i>P values</i>	
<i>Brand Awareness-> Perceived Value</i>	3.05	0.002	3.449	0.001	H1 was supported
<i>Brand Awareness -> Attitude</i>	1.95	0.051	1.906	0.057	H2 was not supported
<i>Perceived Quality -> Perceived Value</i>	9.302	0	6.036	0	H3 was supported
<i>Perceived Quality -> Attitude</i>	0.362	0.717	0.725	0.469	H4 was not supported
<i>Perceived Value -> Attitude</i>	6.845	0	5.031	0	H5 was supported
<i>Attitude -> Purchase Intention</i>	37.699	0	29.793	0	H6 was supported

H1: This study examines the impact of brand awareness on perceived value. The results reveal that brand awareness has a significant and positive effect on perceived value for potential customers ($t= 3.05, p <0.05$). Additionally, existing customers also experience a significant and positive effect ($t= 3.449, p <0.05$). Therefore, the hypothesis (H_1) is supported. This finding is in alignment with Jacob's research. According to [17] and [44], brand awareness is a significant antecedent to perceived value. Research suggests that brand awareness of a food service brand has a positive impact on perceived value.

H2: This study evaluates the potential impact of brand awareness on attitude. The findings indicate that brand awareness does not have a positive and significant effect on potential customers' attitudes ($t= 1.95, p >0.05$), nor on existing customers' attitudes ($t=1.906, p >0.05$). Therefore, H2 is not supported, which contradicts previous research conducted by [13], [45]. This situation may arise from the Sambal Korek DNO brand not being firmly established in the consumers' minds, with its aroma and taste possibly affecting consumer attitudes that are becoming more eager and trusting, ultimately resulting in a favorable impression. When creating or changing a brand, consumers may refer to their existing brand awareness attitudes which can fluctuate over time [46].

H3: This study assesses whether perceived quality has a significant and positive impact on perceived value. The results also showed that perceived quality has a significant and positive effects on perceived value for potential customers ($t= 9.302, p <0.05$) and existing customers ($t= 6.306, p <0.05$). Therefore, H3 was supported. According to this finding, food quality can enhance the value offered to customers. Product quality holds importance for consumers. Before making a purchase, consumers tend to seek information about product quality. A good quality product will positively influence their perception [47]. This finding concurs with earlier research on brand equity [15]–[17], as noted by [17]. Therefore, the quality of food and service orientation towards customers have a significant impact on the perceived value within the restaurant industry of Sambel Branding.

H4: H4 evaluates whether perceived quality has a significant and positive effect on attitude. The findings indicate that perceived quality does not have positive and significant effect on potential customers' attitude ($t= 0.362, p >0.05$), while it has a similar impact on existing customers ($t= 0.725, p >0.05$). Therefore, H4 was not supported. These results contradict previous research [18], [19], [48]. The fourth hypothesis cannot be supported that since Sambel Korek DNO caters to a target market with a low to middle socio-economic status, and offers products that are considered staple foods, customers feel that high food and service quality is a requirement offered by the restaurant, so high food quality and service are not very significant to customers' attitude, it might require a mediating elements, one of which is the perceived value. An additional assumption that requires clarification is that the perceived quality of rival eateries has a greater impact on customer attitude, allowing for a greater range of dining options [49]

H5: This study examines whether perceived value has a significant and positive impact on attitude. The findings indicate that perceived value positively affects attitude for potential customers ($t= 6.845, p <0.05$) and existing customers ($t= 5.031, p <0.05$). Therefore, H5 is supported, which aligns with previous research showing that perceived value has a significantly positive impact on attitude. Perceived value helps to better understand customer satisfaction and behavioural intentions [50], [51].

H6: Evaluation of the significant and positive effect of attitude on purchase intention The results indicate that attitude has a significant and positive effect on purchase intention for potential customers ($t= 37.699, p <0.05$). Similarly, for existing customers,

($t= 29.793, p<0.05$). Therefore, H6 was supported. Research demonstrates that buyers are willing to pay more for a product's distinctive features and when brands cultivate a positive attitude, they can generate favorable purchase intentions. This aligns with prior research indicating a positive correlation between attitude and purchase intention (Omar et al., 2023; Hoque et al., 2018)). Advertising campaigns may stimulate demand by influencing individuals' attitudes, resulting in purchase intention [52]

Table 6. Path Coefficient Comparison of Indirect Effects

	<i>Potential Customers</i>		<i>Existing Customers</i>	
	<i>T statistics</i>	<i>P values</i>	<i>T statistics</i>	<i>P values</i>
<i>Brand Awareness -> Perceived Value -> Attitude</i>	2.854	0.004	3.15	0.002
<i>Brand Awareness -> Attitude -> Purchase Intention</i>	1.872	0.061	1.973	0.049
<i>Perceived Quality -> Perceived Value -> Attitude</i>	3.875	0	5.555	0
<i>Perceived Quality -> Attitude -> Purchase Intention</i>	0.725	0.469	0.363	0.716
<i>Perceived Value -> Attitude -> Purchase Intention</i>	4.92	0	6.442	0
<i>Brand Awareness -> Perceived Value -> Attitude -> Purchase Intention</i>	2.782	0.005	3.122	0.002
<i>Perceived Quality -> Perceived Value -> Attitude -> Purchase Intention</i>	3.832	0	5.244	0

H7a: The study of indirect effects revealed that, for potential customers, Attitude has no mediating effect between brand awareness and purchase intention ($t=1.872; p>0.05$), whereas, for existing customers, Attitude has a mediating effect between brand awareness and intent to purchase ($t=1.973, p<0.05$). This is likely due to the fact that potential customers take other factors into account when deciding where to dine. According to [52] and (Omar et al., 2023) customers who have tried the product may have a favourable or unfavourable opinion depending on their experience and evaluation, which would ultimately affect their future purchase intention.

H7b: Attitude does not mediate the effect between perceived quality and purchase intention for both potential customers ($t=0.725, p>0.05$) and existing customers ($t=-0.363, p=0.716$). This contradicts the findings of [48] research where brand awareness and perceived quality were found to have a significant effect on attitudes and purchase intention. Other variables such as perceived value may affect customer attitude. Previous research indicates that perceived value may act as a mediating variable [16].

H8a: analyze whether perceived value has mediating effects on brand awareness and attitude. From the result, this perceived value has mediating effects on brand awareness and attitude for potential customers ($t=2.8534; p<0.005$) and existing customers ($t= 3.15; p<0.005$)

H8b: analyze whether perceived Value has mediating effects on perceived quality and attitude. From the result, this perceived value has mediating effects on brand awareness and attitude for potential customers ($t=3.875; p<0.005$) and existing customers ($t= 5.555; p<0.005$). Both Hypothesis are supported in this research. The indirect effects of perceived value and attitude demonstrate that brand awareness has a significant impact on purchase intention for both potential customers ($t=2.782, p<0.05$) and existing customers ($t=3.122, p<0.05$). Additionally, perceived value and attitude also have indirect effects from perceived quality to purchase intention for potential customers ($t=3.832, p<0.05$) and existing customers ($t=5.244, p<0.05$). Based on the findings, it can be inferred that consumers in the Spicy Restaurant Branding industry exhibit comparable behaviour. They appear to be price sensitive and consider the cost of the service. Hence, perceived value has a greater influence on their attitude, leading to a positive impact on purchase intentions. Brand recognition and perceived quality, however, do not have a direct impact on customers' attitudes. In addition, perceived value has a mediating effect on perceived quality and attitude within the competitive quick-service restaurant industry. Quality service alone may not suffice to ensure customer return. It seems that the impact of perceived quality on revisit intention is significantly mediated by perceived value (indirect effect). Customers in quick-service restaurants are highly attentive to the quality of service offered and prices charged (Pham et al., 2016). These results emphasize the crucial role of perceived value in the 'sambel'

restaurant branding sector. So, the company needs to concentrate on increasing perceived value to improve customers' attitudes towards the brand and its perceived quality, which can subsequently boost purchase intentions.

D. Explanatory power (Coefficients of determination; R^2)

The coefficient of determination (R^2) is the most frequently used measure to assess the explanatory power of a structural model. It is calculated as the squared correlation between the actual and predicted values of a specific endogenous construct. The coefficient presents the combined effects of exogenous latent variables on the endogenous latent variable. The R-square value assesses to what extent an endogenous construct can be described by an exogenous construct. The R^2 value ranges from 0 to 1, with higher levels indicating greater levels of explanation. The R-square value is used to determine the level of effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable [38]. R-square value of 0.25 indicates a weak model, 0.50 indicates a moderate model, and 0.75 indicates a strong model [35]. Table 7. presents that the variable of attitude could be elucidated by 72% of the model, indicating that brand awareness, perceived quality, and perceived value moderately explain the dependent variable of attitude. Purchase intention could be explained by 81.6% of the model, indicating that the attitude variable strongly explains the dependent variable of purchase intention. The variable of perceived value could be explained by 61.6% of the model, indicating that brand awareness and perceived quality variables moderately explain the dependent variable of perceived value.

Table 7. R-square of potential customers and existing customers

	Potential Customers	Existing Customers
Attitude	0.72	0.727
Perceived Quality	0.616	0.64
Purchase Intention	0.816	0.739

V. CONCLUSION

According to the PLS-SEM analysis, it was found that brand awareness and perceived quality do not directly influence the attitude of both existing and potential customers. However, they have positive and significant effects on attitude through the mediating effect of perceived value. Ultimately, attitude also has a significant influence on purchase intention. The study analyzed food quality and customer-oriented service as the product quality factors. It was concluded that customers and potential customers of Sambel Korek DNO prioritize whether the product can meet their needs and expectations. This study highlights the importance of perceived value in purchase intention at Sambel Branding Restaurant in Jakarta.

VI. RECOMMENDATION

This study concentrates solely on a single Sambel Korek DNO outlet, which is significantly geographically restricted. Additionally, this study solely concentrates on enhancing dine-in customer purchase intention. As a result, any plans to augment purchase intention in other outlet or online orders must be adapted to the outlet's internal and external circumstances, as well as its target audience. Further research should investigate the factors that can enhance perceived value.

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